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Assessing High-Resolution Interactive Lake Modeling via Lake Constance's Influence on Local Climate

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Large water bodies significantly influence local and regional climates, especially in urban settings. However, capturing the complex interplay between mesoscale atmospheric processes, lake-atmosphere feedbacks, and Urban Heat Island (UHI) dynamics remains challenging, particularly under changing climatic conditions. This study uses REgional MOdel (REMO) coupled with the interactive 1-D Freshwater Lake model (FLake) to assess the added value of high-resolution dynamical downscaling and interactive lake modeling.

Simulations are performed at spatial resolutions of 12.5 km and 3 km, enabling a systematic evaluation of the impact of high-resolution dynamical downscaling on the accurate representation of lake-atmosphere interactions and associated mesoscale processes. These 3 km simulations were conducted within the framework of the BMBF-funded project NUKLEUS. Furthermore, this study is part of the EU-funded project FOCAL, which includes an urban pilot in Constance, Germany, aimed at efficiently exploring climate data locally. Key metrics, including mean and extreme temperatures, precipitation, and relevant indices, are analyzed against high-resolution observational datasets provided by the German Weather Service (DWD). Our study investigates the influence of Lake Constance on UHI dynamics within the city of Constance and its surrounding areas, with a focus on how interactive lake modeling affects urban-rural climate gradients. By analyzing both spatial and temporal climate patterns, along with key physical processes such as energy fluxes, wind patterns, and heat exchanges, we assess whether higher spatial resolution leads to a more accurate representation of lake-atmosphere interactions.